

TRESTIMA
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Research on Mediterranean tree species detection using convolutional neural networks

DigiMedFor WP2

1. Introduction

The task was to build an image classifier using convolutional neural networks capable of distinguishing between different tree species commonly found in Mediterranean forests. The dataset was created from a collection of forest images where human annotators had manually marked the locations of tree trunks at the height of one meter. Using these annotations, an edge detection algorithm was utilized to extract complete images of the trunks. Additionally, each trunk was classified by human annotators, providing the necessary labels for the classification task.

Figure 1: A douglas fir trunk image extracted from a forest image

The images were brightened a bit to make tree trunk features more prominent.

2. Dataset

Using all available data and filtering out trees with diameter of below 12 cm, the tree trunk extraction yielded a dataset consisting of 346 douglas fir samples, 5 silver fir samples and 17 pine samples. Convolutional neural networks typically require at least hundreds of samples for each class to be trained effectively, and it is common for each class to have thousands of samples. Due to the limited data available, a decision was made to train a binary classifier to distinguish between douglas fir and other species samples due to the limited data available. Also due to the limited data, the “other species” data was extended to have approximately the same number of samples as the douglas fir data by adding non-Mediterranean conifer trunk images to the set.

The dataset was divided into training, validation, and test sets, with 70% of the samples allocated to the training set, and the remaining 30% evenly split between the validation and test sets. Stratification was used to ensure that class distribution remained balanced across all sets. The seed of the random set division was fixed to ensure that each iteration of the model would have the same amount of easier and harder to recognize trees, e.g. due to foliage obstructing a part of the tree trunk. Due to the relatively small dataset, the test dataset was also small which resulted in high variance between achieved test accuracies.

The image classifier was trained using TensorFlow version 2.17.0.

3. Methodology and results

The tree trunks extracted from the forest images had varying sizes. Neural networks generally expect the input size to be constant, so the images were padded from their original size to the target input size by centering the original image and adding black padding around the images. This method was chosen instead of upscaling the images to the target size to preserve the intricate patterns found on tree bark, which could have happened if the images' aspect ratio were altered. Neural networks perform optimally when the input values are between 0 and 1, so the pixel values of color channels were normalized to this range.

Figure 2: Padding used to make the input size standardized

Initial attempts using a neural network with two convolutional layers led to high training accuracy reaching around 96 % but significantly lower test accuracy of around 57 %, indicating overfitting. Since randomly guessing the classes would yield an accuracy of around 50%, it was clear that the model had learned to identify patterns, indicating that meaningful machine learning was taking place. The goal became clear: improve generalization performance by addressing data augmentation, and model optimization techniques.

Figure 3: Evolution of test accuracy

3.1 Data Augmentation

Several data augmentation techniques were employed to make the training set more diverse, and thus make the model perform better with unseen data. After data augmentations, the test accuracy rose to 64 %.

To increase dataset diversity and reduce overfitting, several augmentation techniques were applied:

Horizontal Flips: Randomly flipping images to simulate different viewing angles.

Color Adjustments: Modifying brightness, contrast, saturation, and hue to account for varying lighting conditions.

Random Zooms: Scaling images to mimic different distances from the camera.

Noise Addition: Introducing Gaussian noise to make the model robust to grainy images.

Cutouts (Occlusions): Randomly occluding parts of images to help the model focus on less prominent features and to simulate foliage etc. obstructing tree trunks.

Figure 4: Top-left is the original image, the other images are examples of data augmentation techniques applied to the image. Zooming, horizontal flips, various color adjustments, gaussian noise and occlusions can be seen.

The following augmentation techniques were also tried but didn't have positive effect on the test accuracy:

Image rotations: Slightly rotating the input images to account for the natural variations in tree growth angles.

Random color channel shuffling: Shuffling the RGB channels to make the model rely less on colors and more on the patterns.

3.2 Transfer learning

Transfer learning is the process of taking a pre-trained network usually trained for a different task, and using parts of it in conjunction with a custom trained network. In this project, transfer learning significantly helped with the classification result, most likely due to the dataset's limited size. Several pre-trained models were tested with TensorFlow's implementation of ResNet50V2 yielding the best results. Using the pre-trained model for feature extraction with a custom classifier at the end of the model for classification boosted the accuracy to 75 %. Unfreezing the last layers of the ResNet50V2 model allowed the model to adapt better to the task, with test accuracy reaching 78 %. Finally, introducing variable learning rate and fine-tuning parameters yielded a test accuracy score of 83 % which ended up being the highest reached accuracy.

3.3 Model Architecture

Base Model: Used a pre-trained ResNet50V2 model from TensorFlow's Keras applications with weights from ImageNet, excluding the top layers. The base model layers were frozen initially to retain pre-trained features, eventually experimental hyperparameter optimization revealed that unfreezing the last 20 layers resulted in higher achieved accuracy.

Custom Classifier: Added custom layers on top of the base model:

Flattening Layer: Converted feature maps to a 1D feature vector.

Dense Layers: Included a fully connected layer with ReLU activation.

Dropout Layer: Set to 50 % to reduce overfitting, the percentage was found experimentally.

Output Layer: Used a sigmoid activation function for binary classification.

Optimizer: Used the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 10^{-4} in conjunction with a learning rate scheduler for fine-tuning.

Loss Function: Binary cross-entropy, for binary classification task.

Callbacks:

Learning Rate Scheduler: Halved the learning rate after every 5 epochs to help with converging to the best solution.

Early Stopping: The training was stopped when validation accuracy didn't improve for 15 consecutive epochs.

Model Checkpoint: Used to restore the model that achieved the highest validation accuracy during training to be used with the test set.

4. Conclusion

Using data augmentation techniques and pre-trained models can significantly increase the rate of differentiating douglas firs from other tree species correctly. While 83 % accuracy is drastically higher than the random guess of 50 %, it is not high enough to reliably predict the correct outcome in most practical applications.

The data augmentation techniques helped to increase the generalization power of the model, but some overfitting still happened. It is very likely that the model would generalize better, and thus perform better with unseen data if the dataset's size was substantially increased.